

Research on Portfolio Investment Decision-Making to Linear and Exponential utility Function based on Triangular Fuzzy Numbers Theory

Arrived Date	Accepted Date	Published Date
15.08.2020	17.08.2020	31.10.2020

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ABSTRACT

In security market, most risk-averse investors would try to avoid relevant risk while seeking their profits. And each investor may possess his utility function and try to choose the optimal portfolio according to the principle of the expected utility maximization. In this paper, we mainly make research on portfolio investment decision-making to linear and exponential utility function based on triangular fuzzy numbers theory. A complete decision-making algorithm based on triangular fuzzy number to represent the optimal portfolio of securities price is proposed. Finally, an illustrative example is given to prove that the decision-making algorithm proposed in the paper is feasible and valid.

INTRODUCTION

In security market, each investor has his own utility function to express the satisfaction of the investment return and try to choose the optimal portfolio according to the principle of expected utility maximization. At the same time, most investors are rational risk-averse investors, so they will try to avoid relevant risk while seeking their returns. So far, many scholars have carried out much research on this problem [1-5]. In the paper[9], portfolio investment decision-making to exponential utility function was researched, so we want to expend it to linear and exponential utility function, which is more general to investors.

In this paper, we mainly make some research on portfolio investment decision-making to linear and exponential utility function based on triangular fuzzy numbers theory [6-9]. And one complete decision-making algorithm is proposed.

To do so, the paper is set out as follows. Firstly, portfolio investment decision-making is introduced, and the linear and exponential utility function is adopted, and triangular fuzzy number is used to express the security price changing process. Secondly, one complete algorithm is given to solve the investor optimal portfolio. Thirdly, an illustrative example is presented. Finally, conclusions and final remarks follow.

Problem Statement and Preliminaries.

In the 1950s, the American Economist and Financier H. Markowitz established his well-known Mean-Variance Model, which suggests that investors will determine the optimal portfolio with the purpose of enhancing their profits and reducing their risks[1].

Suppose that there are n kinds of securities, whose prices at the current moment ($t = 0$) are

$S_{10}, S_{20}, \dots, S_{n0}$, and at a future moment are S_1, S_2, \dots, S_n . Denote $x_i = \ln\left(\frac{S_i}{S_{i0}}\right)$ $i = 1, 2, \dots, n$,

$X_{n \times 1} = (x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n)^T$,

where x_i is the logarithm return rate of the i th security during the period from the time $t=0$ to $t=T$, X is the vector of logarithm return rate of all these n kinds of securities. The return expectation and covariance matrix are represented respectively by the two formulas

$$EX = (EX_1, EX_2 \cdots EX_n)^T = \mu, \quad \text{Var}(X) = E(X - EX)(X - EX)^T = \Sigma.$$

Let ω_i denote the investment proportion of the i th security, $i=1,2,\dots,n$, and let $\omega_{n \times 1} = (\omega_1, \dots, \omega_n)^T$, and the investment proportion must fulfill the condition $\omega^T e = 1$. The investor's corresponding return $R = \omega^T X$ is a random variable. The expected return and variance of R are $r = ER = \omega^T \mu$ and $\sigma^2 = \text{Var}(R) = \omega^T \Sigma \omega$.

The major concern of Markowitz's Mean-Variance model is the problem of constrained extreme value[2,3]: under the condition of $\omega^T \mu = a$, figure out ω to minimize the risk, i.e. to minimize $\text{Var}(\omega^T X) = \omega^T \Sigma \omega$.

So it boils down to a mathematic problem: to figure out the minimum of $\omega^T \Sigma \omega$ under the condition $\omega^T e = 1$ and $\omega^T \mu = a$.

And then we can reach such a conclusion:

$$\omega_* = \frac{C - aB}{\Delta} \Sigma^{-1} e + \frac{aA - B}{\Delta} \Sigma^{-1} \mu, \quad (1)$$

and hence the corresponding variance is

$$\sigma^2(\omega_*) = \omega_*^T \Sigma \omega_* = \frac{1}{\Delta} (Aa^2 - 2Ba + C), \quad (2)$$

where $A = e^T \Sigma^{-1} e$, $B = e^T \Sigma^{-1} \mu = \mu^T \Sigma^{-1} e$, $C = \mu^T \Sigma^{-1} \mu$, $\Delta = AC - B^2$.

In the Portfolio investment of securities, most risk-averse investors will try to avoid relevant risks while seeking their profits. Now, we adopt the linear and exponential utility function, which expresses itself with

$$U = k_1 + k_2 x - k_3 e^{-k_4 x} \quad (k_2, k_3, k_4 > 0)$$

Here x denotes investment return. The linear and exponential utility function is an extended form to exponential utility function $U = -e^{-kx}$ in paper [9].

It is acknowledged in financial mathematics that the investment return is displayed according to Normal Distribution $N(r, \sigma^2)$. The density function of Normal distribution is

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} e^{-\frac{(x-r)^2}{2\sigma^2}},$$

and hence the expectation of exponential utility function is

$$EU = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (k_1 + k_2 x - k_3 e^{-k_4 x}) f(x) dx = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (k_1 + k_2 x - k_3 e^{-k_4 x}) \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}\sigma} \exp\left(-\frac{(x-r)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) dx$$

which is

$$EU = k_1 + k_2 r - k_3 \exp\left(\frac{1}{2} k_4^2 \sigma^2 - k_4 r\right) \quad (3)$$

As this type of utility function is averse to risks, we may employ the non-difference curve method for a possible solution [3,4,5].

Definition. $\tilde{M} = [l, m, u]$ is called a triangular fuzzy number, and its membership function is the following:

$$\mu_{\tilde{M}}(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{x-l}{m-l}, & x \in [l, m]; \\ \frac{u-x}{u-m}, & x \in [m, u]; \\ 0, & \text{others.} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Here, $l < m < u$ are real numbers, as in [6,7,8].

For any triangular fuzzy number $\tilde{M} = [l, m, u]$, according to the definition of the Mean Area of \tilde{M} , we can get

$$s(\tilde{M}) = \frac{(l + 2m + u)}{4} \quad (5)$$

According to the changing characteristic of securities price, we adopt the triangular fuzzy number $\tilde{M} = [l, m, u]$ to express securities price changing process. For one security on one trading day, l denotes the lowest price, m denotes the closing price, u denotes the highest price. And here in general, we suppose $l < m < u$.

Now we give complete decision-making algorithm to investors is proposed to get the optimal portfolio based on the triangular fuzzy number theory.

Suppose on some trading day, n securities price can be expressed as triangular fuzzy number $\tilde{M}_i = [l_i, m_i, u_i], i = 1, 2 \dots n$. And we use the closing price S_{0i} , on the previous trading day for each security as the initial price.

So we can get the return rate in the triangular fuzzy number form as:

$$l'_i = \ln\left(\frac{l_i}{S_{0i}}\right), \quad m'_i = \ln\left(\frac{m_i}{S_{0i}}\right), \quad u'_i = \ln\left(\frac{u_i}{S_{0i}}\right), \quad i = 1, 2 \dots n,$$

then we can get X , so we use formula(5) to express the return rate

$$\mu = [s(\tilde{M}_1), s(\tilde{M}_2) \dots s(\tilde{M}_n)]$$

At the same time, we can get the covariance matrix $\Sigma = (\sigma_{ij})_{n \times n}$

According to the principle of the Mean-Variance Theory, the optimal portfolio is the cut-off point of non-difference and efficient frontier.

Figure 1. Selection of optimal portfolio investment

We may construct the following model:

$$\begin{cases} EU = k_1 + k_2r - k_3 \exp(\frac{1}{2}k_4^2\sigma^2 - k_4r) \\ \sigma^2 = \frac{1}{\Delta}(Ar^2 - 2Br + C) \end{cases} \tag{6}$$

then

$$\begin{aligned} EU &= k_1 + k_2r - k_3 \exp[\frac{1}{2}k_4^2 \cdot \frac{1}{\Delta}(Ar^2 - 2Br + C) - k_4r] \\ &= k_1 + k_2r - k_3 \exp[\frac{1}{2}k_4^2 \cdot \frac{A}{\Delta}r^2 - (k_4^2 \frac{B}{\Delta} + k_4)r + \frac{1}{2}k_4^2 \frac{C}{\Delta}] \end{aligned}$$

By analysis, we can get the maximum solution of EU .

Illustrative Example.

In this section, we present one illustrative example. Suppose their 5 securities, their prices information matrix are Table 1. And suppose some investor utility function is $U = k_1 + k_2x - k_3e^{-k_4x}$, please solve his optimal portfolio investment decision-making[9]?

Table 1. Their prices information matrix Table

Security	The closing prices on 2016.4.28	the lowest prices, the closing prices and the highest prices in the form of triangular fuzzy numbers on 2016.4.29
x_1	76.16	[77.01,78.26,80.44]
x_2	10.51	[9.31,9.57,10.88]
x_3	6.78	[6.02,7.16,7.18.]
x_4	10.32	[9.98,10.56,10.96]
x_5	26.45	[25.36,26.66,27.14]

Step 1. The 5 securities price can be expressed as triangular fuzzy number form as $\tilde{M}'_i = [l'_i, m'_i, u'_i]$

$$\tilde{M}'_1 = [0.0111, 0.0272, 0.0547]; \tilde{M}'_2 = [-0.1213, -0.0937, 0.0346];$$

$$\tilde{M}'_3 = [-0.1189, 0.0545, 0.0573]; \tilde{M}'_4 = [-0.0335, 0.0230, 0.0602];$$

$$\tilde{M}'_5 = [-0.0421, 0.0079, 0.0258];$$

Step 2. Using Matlab, get the return rate and covariance matrix according to the data:

$$\mu = [s(\tilde{M}'_1), s(\tilde{M}'_2), \dots, s(\tilde{M}'_n)]^T = [0.0301, -0.6853, 0.2571, 0.0182, -0.0001]^T,$$

$$\Sigma = (\sigma_{ij})_{5 \times 5} = \begin{bmatrix} 3.0133 & 1.4276 & 0.9079 & 0.8264 & 1.4628 \\ 1.4276 & 0.7081 & 0.3573 & 0.3689 & 0.6269 \\ 0.9079 & 0.3573 & 0.4409 & 0.3010 & 0.5927 \\ 0.8264 & 0.3689 & 0.3010 & 0.2428 & 0.4484 \\ 1.4628 & 0.6269 & 0.5927 & 0.4484 & 0.8481 \end{bmatrix}$$

And from the data, we also get

$$A = -6.7255e+004, B = -4.4548e+004, C = -9.7906e+003, \Delta = AC - B^2 = -1.3261e+009.$$

Step 3. For $U = k_1 + k_2x - k_3e^{-k_4x}$, no losing general, let $k_1 = 0, k_2 = k_3 = k_4 = 1$, then

$U(x) = x - e^{-x}$, and

$$EU = r - \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 - r\right)$$

Step 4. Then we can get the optimal portfolio investment decision-making,

$$\begin{cases} EU = r - \exp\left(\frac{1}{2}\sigma^2 - r\right) \\ \sigma^2 = \frac{1}{-1.3261e+009} ((-6.7255e+004)r^2 - 2*(-4.4545e+004)r + (-9.7906e+003)) \end{cases}$$

Then we can use self-compiled Matlab program to get $r^* = 3.9435e+004$

And the optimal portfolio investment proportion is

$$\omega = (1.0e+004) * [3.2074, -4.2227, 3.3408, 5.1355, -7.4608]^T$$

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In this paper, a complete decision-making algorithm is proposed, which uses triangular fuzzy numbers to represent security prices, and obtains the linear and exponential utility functions of the optimal portfolio. And an illustrative example is given to prove that the decision-making algorithm is feasible and valid.

This work is supported by Natural Science Foundation of Liaoning Province (201601088). The author also gratefully acknowledge the helpful comments and suggestions of the reviewers, which have improved the presentation.

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